

Religious Analysis of Euthanasia in India and Life-Long Learning

Paper Id : 18936 Submission Date : 04/05/2024 Acceptance Date : 19/05/2024 Publication Date : 24/05/2024
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.12703517

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/remarking.php#8>

Shailendra Singh

Research Scholar
Law Department
NIILM University
Kaithal, Haryana, India

R. K. Gupta

Research Guide
Law Department
NIILM University
Kaithal, Haryana, India

Abstract

This paper discusses the art of lifelong learning through religious contexts relating to euthanasia in India. Apart from India, thinkers from other countries have also defined this topic better; an attempt will be made to reach a conclusion by comparing complex topics like euthanasia with the ancient history of education and information in India. Euthanasia has been described in Indian history for centuries, in which the purpose of euthanasia was not only to reduce pain but also to voluntarily give up one's breath until the value of life was achieved. During the long journey of euthanasia from the Treta yuga (ramayna) to dwapara yuga (Mahabharata happened in Dwapara Yuga (5694 BCE to 3102 BCE) to the present era that is called Kalyug, it has reached such a stage that people have lost knowledge about it and it has lost recognition in society and law. Today civilized countries have banned even the right to death which is included in the right to life. In such a situation, no matter how much pain a person is going through, he cannot be given euthanasia. For this, at least the government and law in India should allow euthanasia by encouraging the teaching method of its Vedic traditions; enlightened persons in Indian customs have never compared such death with suicide.

Keywords Euthanasia, Lifelong Learning, Vedic Traditions.

Introduction

Lifelong learning is defined as "all learning activities undertaken throughout the life aimed at improving personal, social and employment-related knowledge, skills and competencies". The aim of education in India has been to emphasize learning since the Treta Yuga (Ramayana took place in Treta Yuga 9582 BCE to 5694 BCE)[1] (as of now, Ramayana is more than 9300 years old and Mahabharata is about 5200 years old) For this, the need for no special teaching curriculum was felt, whereas all the systems of education were systematically established in India since ancient times, be they Vedas, Puranas, Darshana or Vedanga, all of them had special It is described as follows. Arrangements related to specific knowledge, various types of institutions such as Gurukul where education was provided to young children, councils where programs of advanced education were organized in which people of all age groups participated, i.e. there was no fixed age for learning. The main objective of education in the Indian Vedic system was to provide good quality education to the students. The main objective of education was to promote and develop culture, character and personality and to inculcate high ideals in the students. Its objective was to prepare the students for the future and enable them to survive in any situation by developing the mental, physical and intellectual personality of the students.[2] Nalanda in Bihar, Takshashila in Punjab Pakistan, Vallabhi in Gujarat, Salotagi in Karnataka, Ennairam in Tamil Nadu, Ujjain in Madhya Pradesh and Varanasi in Uttar Pradesh are known for religious text.[3]

Objective of study

This research paper includes the following objectives:

1. To bring the ancient religious systems of India in front of the society, which are as effective today as they were at that time, this objective is included in this research paper.
2. Euthanasia in India has been prohibited on the basis of current law, whereas its importance was of high level in Indian mythological system, its objective is also to eliminate this gap.

3. Indian culture has always believed in learning and teaching, its objective is to strengthen that belief in today's time.

4. The objective of the research paper is to attract the attention of thinkers, legislature, judiciary related to the subject of Indian culture.

Review of Literature For this paper many books, research papers, newspaper articles etc has been reviewed which has been discussed through out the paper.

Methodology

The research process that will be used by the researcher in this research is known as social legal research. In which we will take the help of applied research methodology, the researcher will obtain facts and figures from primary and secondary sources to verify his questions and objectives, the survey will be done from the information obtained through available literature, book, and internet. We will solve the problems in our research paper by studying various dimensions through questions, which can benefit the society, through which the researchers will also express their personal views in this research paper. Here we will try to verify our objectives by answering your questions. It has been observed for a long time that ancient and indigenous education systems and their wide multidimensional effects receive considerable attention from both the Indian government and policy makers and educationists. Despite the existence of sufficient theoretical and empirical literature, the evidence about the impact of learning in ancient history is mixed. In this research work, the researcher will review and analyse the literature of the selected topic and analyse in his report how gaining information through history has an overall positive impact on the continuous process of learning beyond education and educated society.

Research question

A- Is the practice of long life learning, beyond education in India found in history in the context of Euthanasia?

Analysis

Research Question A- Is the practice of long life learning, beyond education in India found in history in the context of Euthanasia?

The scientific word "Euthanasia" comes from Greek mythology "Eu" meaning good and "Thanatos" meaning death, constitutently meaning death by one's wish. The term euthanasia has been practised and condemned by various communities and civilizations of different era.[4] When we talk about euthanasia, which is called euthanasia in Latin language, in India many sages have been giving up their lives as per their wish, which has been legally recognized since the Vedic period, like river Ganga son "Bhishma Pitamah" sacrificed his life in Mahabharata. Unless he voluntarily renounced them, which was a form of learning in which one had mastered the art of awakening one's Kundalis and also it was in the Mahabharata that Arjuna's son Abhimanyu attempted to break the Chakravyuh in his mother's womb. The art of breaking was learned in the mother's womb when Arjuna's was teaching this art to his wife in the bedroom, which shows that there is no age for learning.[5]

Research Question B- Hinduism-Suicide-(Euthanasia) - Can Hindu beliefs on euthanasia is advanced on the basis of knowledge of religious texts?

It has been pointed out that the term self-immolation for suicide in Hinduism condemned the purpose of killing oneself for deliberate narrow mindedness. This was a situation in which the Dharma Sutras curiously prohibited suicide. By the way, Hinduism prefers enlightened persons who deliberately chose a beneficial way of death. Self-immolation is recorded as various examples of romantic demise in paintings on temples and sacred places. In the present times parents should provide their children with the best possible education as an investment that matches their culture, civilization, thoughts and conduct, which will benefit the entire society in the future. Thus, education is the most important step in the development of a country and everyone should promote it to the highest level. [6] In Indian customs, enlightened persons have never compared such death with suicide. Rather, it has been consistently observed that suicide leads to problems in later life. Here special mention of the Indian attitude towards life and death is necessary. In Hindu convention, every Image and model is used to refer to the path through which the bonds that confuse man's self or soul with vast transience can be completely broken and through which the extremes of permanent state and opportunity can be attained. The goals can be achieved ultimately and unquestionably.

Conclusion Everyone has a different attitude towards death, but in India it has a very old and golden history. Since there is enough evidence of this in religious texts in India, we should take inspiration from our religious texts to learn beyond education. The Indian government

should include this information in existing schemes and its school curriculum. However, one should remain calm and balanced even in adverse circumstances. Along with these advancements, there has been a progressive change in the attitude of doctors, whose ultimate goal is that they are ready to do anything to keep their patients alive. Although researcher do not blame these efforts or advancements in innovation, researcher believes that the conditions in which patients and their families live are not a means of a decent life, and these are matters of thought that we should consider. The only meaning of being educated is to accept change. If we do not accept change while our mythological texts support positive change in the current situation, then it will be a big mistake.

References

- 1.(<https://www.quora.com/What-is-the-timeline-of-Ramayana-and-Mahabharat-E-g-XYZ-BC-Also-which-civilizations-were-present-in-the-world-at-that-exact-time>)
2. (Mangesh M. Ghonge, Submitted: 03 July 2020 Reviewed: 17 July 2020 Published: 27 October 2020)
- 3.(<https://testbook.com/question-answer/match-the-following-historic-places-with-their-dis--5ee0d9bb11729c0d0eadd0dc>)
4. (Helga, 2017, Retrieved 6july 2017) Helga, A. f. (2017, Retrieved 6july 2017, August). Euthanasia .
5. (hydrabad) hydrabad, i. i. (n.d.). *teacher training on the learning brain*. Retrieved from IIIT-H | The International Institute of Information Technology – Hyderabad.
6. Bansal, R. (2020, January 4th). Is education the most important step in the development of the country? *the times of India*